

HIERARCHICAL COMPOSITES COMBINING NANOSCALE REINFORCEMENTS WITH CONVENTIONAL FIBRES

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SUMMARY

Hierarchical composites introduce nanoscale fillers into the matrix of conventional fibre composites, in order to address critical failure modes. The effectiveness of growing carbon nanotubes onto primary fibres is reported at the single-fibre level. The success of an analogous, entirely renewable and biodegradable hierarchical composite system provides encouragement to scale-up.

Keywords: Nanocomposites, nanotubes, multiscale, hybrid, hierarchical

INTRODUCTION

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have generated huge activity in composites science due to their low density, high aspect ratio, intrinsically superior mechanical properties and remarkable electrical and thermal properties. Many studies have reported the production and characterisation of CNT-based polymer composites [1, 2]. Although promising results have been obtained, progress has been limited by several factors, including nanotube synthesis (quality), dispersion, alignment and interfacial bonding. On the other hand, traditional fibre-reinforced composites are currently used in a wide range of fields; although they have excellent in-plane properties, the relatively weak compression and transverse properties remain a major issue [3]. One desirable possibility is to introduce CNTs into conventional composites to form a hierarchical or multiscale structure [4-7]. The approach aims to exploit the CNT performance to address the critical (matrix-dominated) failure modes of conventional fibre composites, notably the longitudinal compression and interlaminar performance. The presence of the CNTs at the fibre surface is likely to enhance the fibre/matrix interfacial strength, thus improving the delamination resistance. Whilst reinforcement radial to the fibres, extending into the surrounding matrix, will inhibit fibre microbuckling, which is the critical failure mode under compressive loading [8].

The CNTs can either be dispersed into the matrix prior to impregnation of the fibres, or grown directly onto the surface of the primary dry fibres. Both approaches have advantages and disadvantages. The first route is relatively simple, but particular techniques are needed to avoid self-filtration and problems with high viscosities. The

grafting route simplifies composite processing, and in principle provides an optimised radial geometry, but can damage the primary fibres.

CNT-grafted fibres

CNTs were grafted onto both silica (see Fig. 1) and a range of carbon fibres (see Fig. 2), using a CVD approach. In the case of the silica (Silfa) fibres, metal catalyst was deposited onto the fibre either during the nanotube growth, using an organometallic precursor injected with the hydrocarbon feedstock. On carbon fibres (Sigri C320 or Hexcel IM7), the catalyst was pre-deposited using an incipient wetness technique. The grafted length and density was varied systematically by varying the process parameters, such as temperature, degree of surface oxidation, and catalyst loading. Single fibre tensile testing showed that the silica fibres maintained or improved their stiffness, although not their strength. The tensile strength of the carbon fibres, similarly, tended to be degraded; however, the decrease was minimised by adjusting the growth parameters.

Fig. 1. SEM images of Silfa silica fibres after CNT grafting, using different growth times: (a) 12 min and (b) 15 min.

Fig. 2. SEM images of (a), (b) C320 [7] and (c), (d) IM7 carbon fibres; (a), (c) before and (b), (d) after the CNT grafting.

Single fibre pull-out, push-out, and fragmentation were performed in order to establish the impact of the nanotubes on the interfacial characteristics of the fibres. Pull-out and push-out tests were performed in a conventional epoxy matrix (Fig. 3), but fragmentation tests were based on PMMA (Fig. 4), due to the greater strain to failure. In the case of push-out testing of heavily nanotube grafted carbon fibres, the interfacial shear strength (IFSS) was unchanged; an unusual internal failure of the fibre was observed using electron microscopy, consistent with surface damage by the catalyst metal particles. In all other cases, the IFSS was significantly increased, suggesting a likely improvement in composite properties (see next section). Pull-out tests on C320 carbon fibres showed an IFSS that increased by 60% on grafting nanotubes, whilst fragmentation tests yielded improvements of 26% and 80-150% for IM7 and Silfa fibres, respectively.

Fig. 3. Schematic diagrams of the proposed failure mechanisms for (a) single fibre pull-out and (b) push-out before and after growing CNTs onto fibre surfaces [7].

Fig. 4. Typical dark field optical micrographs of the fibre/PMMA composite specimens tested using the single fibre fragmentation tests. (a) As-received and (b) CNT-grafted silica fibres, (c) as-received and (d) CNT-grafted IM7 carbon fibres. The white areas represent the cracks and the arrows indicate the fragment length.

One critical question is the nature of the interfacial attachment of the nanotubes to the primary fibres. Using advanced sectioning techniques, we have examined the interface using transmission electron microscopy, in the case of the silica fibres. In this case, the metal particles, which act as the catalysts for nanotube growth, clearly etch into the surface by around one diameter. Other Raman, thermogravimetric, and microscopy data establish that the nanotubes are produced by a so-called ‘base-growth’ mechanism, confirming that the metal particles at the primary surfaces are the active catalysts, and link the micro- and nano-fibre scales.

Cellulose nanofibre grafted natural fibres

A green (biodegradable and renewable) analogue to the carbon system was successfully produced by growing bacterial cellulose nanofibres onto the surface of natural plant fibres (see Fig. 5) [9]. In the best system (based on sisal), the mechanical properties of the primary natural fibres were maintained, throughout variations modifications, including the growth of the nanofibres and various washing stages (see Table 1).

Fig. 5. SEM image of bacterial cellulose grown onto the surface of a sisal fibre.

Table 1. Single fibre tensile properties of sisal fibres and their interfacial shear strength within a PLLA matrix, after various modifications [9].

Treatment	Tensile Strength / MPa	Young's Modulus / GPa	IFSS / MPa
Unmodified (Sisal-N)	383 ± 25	15.2 ± 0.9	12.1 ± 0.5
Bacterial cellulose modified (Sisal-NBC)	351 ± 26	14.5 ± 0.3	14.6 ± 1.2
Acetone treated (Sisal-A)	396 ± 48	16.4 ± 1.4	9.5 ± 0.7
Acetone treated and bacterial cellulose modified (Sisal-ABC)	352 ± 27	15.2 ± 1.7	Internal Failure

The introduction of the nanofibre produced a significant improvement in interfacial shear strength, as observed in single fibre pull-out tests, although the effect was smaller than in the carbon nanotubes based systems. The modified sisal fibres were incorporated into a bio-derived polymer matrix, poly(L-lactic acid) (PLLA), to obtain a new class of hierarchical composite. The system is thus both entirely bio-derived and biodegradable. The tensile strength and stiffness of uniaxial, compression-moulded beams was improved both parallel and perpendicular to the primary fibres (see Table. 2). The rate of water uptake and maximum equilibrium water content, critical problems for natural fibre composites, were reduced, offering a potential further benefit. These results are both promising in their own right, and encourage further development of the analogous, all carbon system.

Table 2. Tensile properties and water adsorption rates (α) and maximum moisture uptake for of 34 wt% sisal/PLLA composites. The tensile strength of pure PLLA film was measured to be 64 MPa, with the Young's Modulus of 2.5 GPa [9].

Sisal Fibre	0° Fibre Orientation		90° Fibre Orientation		Rate water adsorption	Water uptake
	σ / MPa	E / GPa	σ / MPa	E / GPa	α / % h ^{-1/2}	%
Sisal-N	78.9 ± 8.5	7.91 ± 0.77	10.0 ± 1.3	2.09 ± 0.05	33.9 ± 1.0	50.0 ± 2.8
Sisal-ABC	113.8 ± 8.1	11.21 ± 0.69	16.8 ± 2.4	3.12 ± 0.10	28.9 ± 0.3	36.6 ± 0.4
Sisal-A	43.9 ± 3.7	3.97 ± 0.20	1.0 ± 0.1	0.30 ± 0.07	30.9 ± 0.6	47.4 ± 4.3

Conclusions

Hierarchical fibre constructs have great promise as a means of improving composite performance. Growth of nanofibres onto the surface of primary fibre reinforcements provides is a convenient processing routes, potentially providing high loading fractions and optimal orientations. The nanoscale reinforcement improves the IFSS between fibre and matrix, leading to improved overall mechanical properties, in the natural fibre systems. Similar improvements can be anticipated, from a higher performance base, for the all carbon system. The addition of the nanofibres can provide other benefits, for example water resistance for the natural fibre system, or other functional benefits using carbon nanotubes; for, example, increased electrical conductivity for lightning strike protection or damage detection.

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